

MORPHOGENESIS OF COLLOID DYSTROPHY AND FOLLICULAR ATROPHY IN THE THYROID GLAND DURING CHEMOTHERAPY OF BREAST CANCER

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is the most common oncological disease among women worldwide, and paclitaxel-based chemotherapy remains one of the primary treatment modalities. However, the adverse effects of chemotherapeutic agents on endocrine glands, particularly the thyroid gland, have not yet been sufficiently investigated. The thyroid gland plays a central role in regulating the body's metabolic processes, immune function, and regenerative capacity. Therefore, studying the morphofunctional changes in thyroid tissue under the influence of paclitaxel is of significant relevance for both morphology and clinical oncology.

Aim. To identify the morphofunctional changes in thyroid follicles, thyrocytes, and the microcirculatory bed in a DMBA-induced breast cancer model under paclitaxel-based chemotherapy.

Materials and Methods. The experiment was conducted in two groups: Group 1 — healthy control rats (n=40); Group 2 — rats with DMBA-induced breast cancer receiving paclitaxel chemotherapy (n=27). Thyroid gland sections were stained using H&E, Van Gieson, and Alcian Blue methods. Morphometric analysis was performed separately in the central and peripheral zones of the gland. Statistical significance was assessed using Student's t-test (p<0.05).

Results. The following significant changes were identified in the chemotherapy group compared to the control group:

— Follicle diameter decreased in the central zone from 39.07±1.89 μm to 31.09±1.76 μm, and in the peripheral zone from 42.73±0.25 μm to 36.74±0.19 μm; follicle area in the central zone decreased from 1258.69±31.52 to 983.58±27.63 μm² (p<0.05).

— Thyroid epithelial cell height decreased in the central zone from 7.73±0.24 μm to 5.50±0.24 μm, and in the peripheral zone from 6.84±0.26 μm to 4.91±0.15 μm (p<0.05).

— Colloid index decreased in the central zone from 36.57±0.76% to 30.02±0.7%, and in the peripheral zone from 43.09±0.84% to 35.48±0.7% (p<0.05).

— Capillary diameter in the central zone decreased from $12.62 \pm 0.41 \mu\text{m}$ to $9.48 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{m}$, and capillary density decreased from 141.08 ± 2.42 to 112.34 ± 2.63 ($p < 0.05$).

— The number of interfollicular C-cells decreased in the central zone from 11.27 ± 0.09 to 7.84 ± 0.25 , and in the peripheral zone from 23.15 ± 0.1 to 18.43 ± 0.27 ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion. Paclitaxel-based chemotherapy induces follicular atrophy, dystrophic changes in thyrocytes, colloid dystrophy, and microcirculatory disturbances in the thyroid gland. The reduction in C-cell count indicates a decline in calcitonin synthesis. These morphological changes confirm the thyrotoxic effect of chemotherapy and justify the need for developing biocorrection strategies.

